

Formulaic expression in Latin mathematical texts: a corpus-driven approach

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Introduction

In this paper, we discuss the peculiar formulaicity of mathematical writing by taking as an example the translation of one Ancient Greek mathematical work.

Formulaic language is an essential feature of scientific writing. The formulaicity of contemporary academic writing, for instance, and the techniques to extract formulaic sequences in academic papers, have been widely investigated (see, for instance, Kermes & Teich 2012 and Iwatsuki et al. 2022 for a literature review of recent studies). In contrast, the specific analysis of mathematical writing is less extended. As Cunningham 2016 points out, however, "The formulaic nature of mathematics is present not simply in the use of mathematical formulae, but also in the use of symbolic shorthand for prose. For instance, the expressions such that, if and only if, for all, and there exists each have a simplified notation [...] that removes the need to write out such expressions. This symbolic notation leads to uniformity and interpretability. The notation often comes with a specific learned meaning and verbal equivalent when read that seems to be evidence of their being processed as single units. These units may then be formulaic sequences, prefabricated language segments treated as wholes in one's memory".

The use of symbolic sequences is a distinctive feature of modern mathematical texts. On the contrary, when it comes to ancient mathematical works (e.g. the Ancient Greek corpus), the text was written in full natural language, but relied heavily on formulaic sequences in order to convey different recurrent items of information. Netz 2003 provides a detailed analysis of the use of formulae in the shaping of mathematical reasoning in the ancient world. With this paper, we aim to compare the taxonomy of linguistic mathematical formulae proposed by Netz with the results of a corpus-driven analysis of one piece of Latin mathematical writing. For the corpus-driven approach, we follow Biber 2009.

The corpus used is the neo-Latin translation of the Archimedean treatises by Jacopo da San Cassiano. The (Latin) translations represent a fascinating case, since they start by being literal "Latinizations" of the original Greek (as Moerbeke's translation of the

13th century, see Clagett 1976), while later translations, such as the 19th-20th century Latin translation accompanying Heiberg's critical edition of the Greek text, start to include mathematical symbols. The long-term goal of our investigation will be to analyse the shift from linguistic to symbolic formulae in this corpus. For this first proof of concept, however, we focus on Jacopo's translation of one work, *The Spirals*, which is the shortest treatise of the Archimedean corpus and is constituted by one dedicatory letter to Dositheus and 18 propositions.

The paper is structured as follows: in Section 1 we contextualise Jacopo's translation and discuss the preprocessing of the text; in Section 2, we discuss the methodology and in Section 3 present our results.

Section 1: Jacopo Da San Cassiano's translation of Archimedes corpus

Jacopo Da San Cassiano translated the part of the Archimedean corpus that circulated in Italy in the 15th century (ca 1450). As a humanist, he intended to render the text in a readable Latin. Consequently, his translation differed greatly from Moerbeke's (it is unclear whether Jacopo had access to this translation). The translation was a great success, and, besides being copied into several manuscripts, it was associated with the *edition princeps* of Archimedes (1544) (see D'Alessandro & Napolitani 2014). D'Alessandro and Napolitani have identified the autograph of the translation (the manuscript Nouv. Acq. Lat. 1538), which was translated by the PhD student Beatrice Sisana using MauroTex, a specific Latex-based language for the critical edition of Latin mathematical texts. The markup identifies, for instance, the mathematical letters. Taking advantage of this high-quality and enriched transcription we proceeded to preprocess the text for this study.

First, we removed all markup elements, apart from the \$\$ used to single out mathematical letters. Second, the whole transcription was verified by a classics student implementing consistent choices in view of the NLP processing (e.g. consistently adding strong punctuation marks even when not included in the manuscript, if other layout elements, such as the end of paragraph, indicated the end of the sentence). The text was then tokenised on sentence and word level using NLTK. Finally, every mathematical letter was replaced by a 'X', and the associated markup was stripped. In this way, we keep the abstract value of "special symbol", but the counting of occurrences is not influenced by the specific letter chosen for the point, since the labels

don't bear any semantic meaning (see Acerbi 2020 for a discussion on the abstract properties of these labels). The only semantic information signified by these letters is their number (i.e. every category of geometrical objects is indicated by a specific number of letters: one for the points, two for the line, etc.). This information is preserved by our replacement. For instance, the sentence "Constat igitur $\alpha\beta$ eandem habere ad $\gamma\delta$ proportionem quam habet $\epsilon\zeta$ ad $\eta\theta$ ", becomes "Constat igitur XX eandem habere ad XX proportionem quam habet XX ad XX".

Section 2. Methodology:

The term formula is used to identify a wide array of linguistic phenomena, from idioms (such as "kick the bucket") to situational utterances such as "How can I ever repay you?" (Wray 2002). As a consequence, adopting one definition of formula, with a clearly associated retrieval method, proves impossible. In the case of (ancient) mathematical texts, several studies have highlighted the regularity of mathematical language (Heath 1987, Mugler 1958, Aujac 1984), but, to the best of our knowledge, the only systematic study of formulaicity is found in Netz 2003. In Chapter 4, Netz discusses the formulae that constitute the backbone of ancient Greek mathematical writing. Based on his extended knowledge of the corpus and of the functioning of ancient geometrical reasoning, he proposes a taxonomy which we briefly recall below.

First, Netz introduces "**object formulae**", i.e. fixed expressions used to identify specific geometrical objects or simple relations (such as proportions). Simple object formulae are simply built on the article and a list of letters (labels) indicating geometrical points (examples are taken from Netz 2003).

1. ἡ AB – 'the (fem.) {2 letters or more}' – line
2. ἡ ὑπὸ τῶν ABΓ – 'the (fem.) by the (*gen. pl. fem.*) {3 letters}' – Angle: 'the (fem.) by the (*fem. gen. pl.*) {3 letters}' is, when fully unpacked, 'the angle contained by the lines AB, BC'. The italicised element is formula '1'.

Secondly, Netz introduces "**construction formulae**", which are syntactic structures used to construct complex geometrical objects, as in: "ἦχθω {formula 1: line} ἐπιψαύουσα, 'let the tangent {formula 1: line} be drawn'. As this example already shows, formulae are frequently embedded in one another.

The third category introduced by Netz consists of "**second-order formulae**", linguistic constructions used to convey the structure of the argument. For instance: ὁμοίως δὴ δεῖξομεν, 'so similarly we will prove . . .'.

The fourth and last category consists of "**argumentation formulae**" that are used to validate an argument. Netz proposes as an example structures such as:

{formula for proportion} καὶ ἀναστρέψαντι {formula for proportion} – 'conversely'

Here, the sequence of the two proportions represents the argument to move to the following step of the reasoning. Again, the embedded nature of the discussed formulae is clearly shown.

The formulae include very different structures linguistically-wise: whereas object formulae are relatively short and fixed sequences, argumentation formulae include two complex parts (the two proportions linked by the adverb) linked via the different adverbs listed by Netz. Such variability makes it a hard exercise to automatically retrieve the formulae without any kind of annotation of the text.

On the other hand, Biber 2009 proposes to adopt a corpus-driven (Tognini-Bonelli 2001) approach in the study of formulaicity and to categorise formulae based on what kind of sequences are retrieved when using different statistical approaches, namely frequency and association strength (i.e. using the Pointwise Mutual Information score). The corpus analysed by Biber comprises academic writing, and the scholar concludes that two different types of sequences are extracted based on the metric used: high-frequency word sequences, which are called "multi-word formulaic sequences"—including function and content words such as in discourse frame sequences; and groups of words with high PMI score such as technical terms that might not occur frequently but do always occur together.

In this paper, we complement these two statistical methods with the algorithm introduced by Koolen and Hoekstra 2022. In this case, the starting point are sequences of words occurring and co-occurring more frequently than a certain threshold. They are then expanded by looking at words that highly likely precede or follow the initial unit (the implementation and theoretical background of the algorithm are described in the paper cited). Parameters such as the length of the initial unit, the frequency threshold

and the length of the expansion are corpus-dependent. Given the small size of the text we are working with, we use:

- sequences of two words as "basic unit"
- words occurring at least twice in the text, and bigrams occurring at least twice
- we expanded up to six words to the left and right of the initial bigram.

The advantage of this approach is that the length of the formula is not fixed in advance (only the maximal length, here being 8, i.e. 2 + 6). As the results will show, identifying the boundaries of formulae is one of the main challenges in retrieving formulae. In this experiment, we kept the expansion to the left and to the right separate. In addition, the approach allows the finding of alternative realisations of the formulae, for instance, cases in which a fixed sequence has a variable element. This is particularly effective for texts where the spelling is not stable and where the same schema can be used for different purposes (i.e. a line can be longer or shorter than another one).

We also include one "adjusted" frequency measure. When calculating the adjusted measure of a sequence, we count every time that sequence occurs and is not included in a longer repeated sequence. An example is provided in Table 1 (Soffiantini and Fantoli, forth.).

Raw frequency (<i>f</i>)	Adjusted frequency (<i>af</i>)
<i>Et ob id dixi</i> : $f = 3$	<i>Et ob id dixi</i> : $af = 3$ (no longer repeated sequences include this one)
<i>Et ob id</i> : $f = 28$	<i>Et ob id</i> : $af = \text{raw frequency of } et\ ob\ id \text{ minus the adjusted frequency of longer sequences including it, here } et\ ob\ id\ dixi.$
<i>Sed ob id</i> : $f = 30$	
<i>Ob id</i> : $f = 155$	$af = 28 - 3 = 25$
	<i>Sed ob id</i> : $af = 30$ (no longer repeated sequences include this one)
	<i>Ob id</i> : $af = 155 - 25 - 30 - 3 = 97$
	(we subtract the <i>af</i> of <i>et ob id dixi</i> , <i>et ob id</i> , <i>sed ob id</i>)

Table 1: Comparison (on a fake example) between raw and adjusted frequency of repeated sequences

Our goal with this paper is to analyse the sequences retrieved by the different tests considering the classification of Netz: do the sequences retrieved fall into the categories identified by Netz? Can we see different categories emerging from the different tests?

Section 3. Results

Following Biber, we start by retrieving the most frequent bigrams, trigrams and quadrigrams. The results are shown in Table 2, where the frequency is indicated between brackets.

bigrams	trigrams	quadrigrams
XX XX (255)	XX XX XX (123)	XX XX XX XX (90)
XX ad (173)	XX ad XX (96)	contentum sub XX XX (58)
XX et (125)	sub XX XX (73)	X X X X (55)
ad XX (116)	X X X (69)	sub XX XX et (46)
X X (88)	XX XX et (60)	ad contentum sub XX (32)
sub XX (84)	contentum sub XX (60)	tertiam partem quadrati XX (21)
contentum sub (66)	ad contentum sub (33)	quam XX ad XX (20)
proportionem quam (58)	partem quadrati XX (26)	XX XX et tertiam (20)
X et (58)	quam XX ad (25)	XX et tertiam partem (20)
quadrati XX (45)	in puncto X (25)	et tertiam partem quadrati (17)

Table 2: Most frequent bigrams, trigrams and quadrigrams

As can be seen, mathematical variables are predominant in this group. Beyond the list of variables, more structured expressions include *ad XX* (indicating the second term of a proportion), *contentum sub XX*, *quadrati XX*, *partem quadrati XX*, *in puncto X*, and the different 'fragments' of the long expression *proportionem quam (habet) XX ad XX*, or *et tertiam partem quadrati XX*. Some of these formulae are (part of) object formulae, such as *quadrati XX*, the sequence expressing the proportion between two lines. Other formulae are nominal phrases which represent fragments of construction formulae, such as *in puncto X* etc. The embedded nature of mathematical formulae also emerges: in the trigram *partem quadrati XX*, we can see the bigram *quadrati XX*; in the trigram *contentum sub XX*, we can see the bigrams *contentum sub* and *sub XX*. Finally,

the list demonstrates the problem of identifying the boundaries of formulae. For example, *sub XX*, *contentum sub*, *contentum sub XX*, *ad contentum sub*, *contentum sub X et* can be combined in a longer string: *ad contentum sub X(X) XX*. The different substrings of the *proportionem quam habet XX ad XX* expression were already discussed.

Table 3 reports the results of the adjusted frequency statistics, with the adjusted frequency between brackets.

Bigrams	Trigrams	Quadrigrams
X X (13)	XX XX XX (33)	XX XX XX XX (33)
esto itaque (9)	X X X (7)	X X X X (12)
quod autem (8)	linea recta ad (6)	XX ad ipsam XX (4)
ipsius X (8)	ad angulos rectos (6)	XX quae sit XX (3)
linea quae (7)	ad lineam XX (5)	et in circulo linea (3)
habet ad (7)	si esse potest (5)	ei quod continetur sub (3)
lineam XX (7)	in hoc libro (4)	ostendendum est quod XX (3)
XX linea (7)	ex ijs quae (4)	ex xx in xx
ad X (7)	a spirali linea (4)	non est igitur xx
extra circulum (7)	ita ut XX (4)	et initium lineae spiralis

Table 3: Most frequent bigrams, trigrams and quadrigrams based on "adjusted frequency".

First of all, the frequency values drop. This means that shorter sequences are very often embedded in several, longer, repeated sequences. This confirms that the formulaicity of mathematical texts is highly "modular" and that frequency counts are not very suited for capturing this dimension. Secondly, different kinds of sequences emerge in comparison with the "raw" frequency: *esto itaque*, *quod autem*, *ostendendum est quod XX*, *si esse potest*, *in hoc libro*, *non est igitur XX* form units that can be considered second-order formulae, or at least formulae that contribute to structure the text. Sequences such as *linea quae*, *extra circulum*, *et initium lineae spiralis*, *a spirali linea*, *linea recta ad*, *ad angulos rectos*, *ei quod continetur sub*, *et in circulo* linea seem fragments of construction formulae. Overall, the cases of

overlapping sequences are reduced, and more space is left for linguistic units representing, for instance, nominal phrases or even simple clauses.

Following Biber, we can expect that n-grams selected based on their high PMI score are of a different kind than the sequences described until now. Table 4 shows the results of such selection:

Bigrams	Trigrams	Quadrigrams
koni rectanguli (2)	locum unde moueri (3)	spaeram plano sic secare(2)
revolutio facta (2)	revolutio facta fuerit (2)	quotcumque numero consequenter disponantur (2)
hac divisione (2)	earum terminos iungit (2)	dum tamen dicta proportio (2)
angulus contentus (2)	aequali excessu superant (2)	una pauciores illis magnitudine (3)
excessu superant (2)	tertiaie partes quadratorum (2)	datam spaeram plano sic (2)
dum tamen (4)	incidunt quarum maxima (2)	frustis similibus sint compositae (2)
positum fuerat (4)	numero consequenter disponantur (2)	sese aequali excessu superant (2)
figurae circumscriptae (3)	quotcumque numero consequenter (2)	queque non habeat terminum (2)
separatum falsum (3)	datam dum tamen (2)	multitudine quidem una pauciores (2)
terminos iungit (2)	plano sic secare (2)	frustorum ex quibus componitur (2)

Table 4: Bigrams, trigrams and quadrigrams with the highest PMI scores occurring at least twice in the text.

It is striking that mathematical variables do not appear in these sequences, which is to be expected: very frequent words are not usually strongly associated with other words. Fragments of object formulae appear in *angulus contentus*, *figurae circumscriptae*,

locum unde moueri, frustorum ex quibus componitur and construction formulae in *quotcumque numero consequenter disponantur, frustis similibus sint compositae*. Verbal phrases such as *earum terminus iungit, plano sic secare* or *sese aequali excessu superant* express typical steps of geometrical reasoning, and might be compared to the argumentation formulae listed by Netz. It should be noted, however, that in most of the cases, it is difficult to identify a linguistic unit with precise meaning without also retrieving the contexts of the text snippet. In addition, the sequences selected by PMI have very low frequencies, which makes it problematic to define them as formulaic within the text.

Finally, we retrieved the sequences using the Koolen-Hoekstra algorithm and the parameters described in Section 2 (Methodology). Sequences of different lengths (from 8 to 3 tokens) are retrieved, for a total of 623 unique formulae. In Table 5, we list formulae obtained by expanding both to the left and to the right, and we show examples of different lengths. The examples are not ranked by "strength" of the formula as in the other two cases.

left	right
quidem praedictis equales magnitudine uero unaquaeque aequalis maximae	frusta a lineis sese aequaliter excedentibus confecta dempto
quae faciunt angulos aequales ad x uersus circumferentiam	minorem habent proportionem quam quadratum xx ad
quod figura circumscripta minor est circulo	punctum quod est principium lineae spiralis
ex frustis similibus sint compositae	spirali in prima reuolutione descripta
ipsam a centro ductam	in uno igitur puncto
similiter autem ostendetur	linea quaedam recta

Table 5: examples of sequences retrieved with the Koolen-Hoekstra algorithm. In bold the "seed" bigram which is expanded by the rest of the formula.

The chunks of sentences emerging with this algorithm are closer to linguistic units (i.e. nominal phrases, or entire clauses) with respect to the sequences extracted by (adjusted) frequency and PMI score. Sequences such as *punctum quod est principium lineae spiralis*, or *ex frustis similibus sint compositae* fall into the category of "construction formulae", whereas *linea quaedam recta* identifies a mathematical object. *Similiter autem ostendetur* belongs to the category of "second-order formulae". Furthermore, several variations of the same formula are returned by the algorithm. For instance, all the following sequences are returned:

- et duae terciae ipsius xx,
- et duae terciae quadrati xx,
- et duae tertiae ipsius xx,
- et duae tertiae quadrati xx,

Here, neither orthographic variations nor the use of pronouns prevent the retrieval of the sequence. The same happens also for longer formulae where the variation is due to the expression of similar mathematical relations:

- 'habeat x ad x maior proportione quam',
- 'habeat x ad x minorem proportionem quam',

Or to stylistic variation:

- 'frusta a lineis sese aequaliter excedentibus confecta dempto',
- 'frusta a lineis sese aequaliter excedentibus contenta dempto',

As such, the algorithm is able to tackle the issues derived from the taste for variation typical of Latin scientific writing and the lack of orthographic standardisation of the manuscript.

Section 4. Conclusions

As we can see, the different algorithms yield different types of formulae. Raw frequency returns mostly sequences with mathematical variables, or parts of object formulae, but it appears particularly difficult to single out formulae with a full meaning. Adjusted frequency, on the contrary, allows construction formulae and second order formulae to

emerge, with clearer linguistic units. PMI score entirely skips sequences with mathematical variables, a result which significantly differs from the previous cases. Expressions with high PMI scores belong to mathematical vocabulary used to define objects and construct them, as well as to (fragmented) sequences of argumentation formulae, i.e. sequences that introduce key passages of the mathematical reasoning. The Koolen-Hoekstra algorithm, finally, provides a large variety of sequences that can be classified into object, construction and second-order formulae, and the full list provides examples of stylistic, mathematical and orthographic variation.

In general, there isn't a very strong association between one measure and one kind of formula, and parts of all typologies are retrieved by each algorithm. Hence, this paper doesn't allow to conclude that there is a strong association between linguistic properties and the mathematical categories defined by Netz.

The Koolen-Hoekstra algorithm partially overcomes what appears to be the main challenge faced, i.e. the great variation in length of the different categories of formulae proposed by Netz, which is partially due to the fact that they are frequently embedded. Whereas more traditional approaches such as frequency and PMI score identify object formulae and, to a certain extent, second-order formulae, longer construction formulae are retrieved in their entirety only by the last algorithm. Hence, in the future we will experiment again by working on the parameters and testing the algorithm and the whole set of Archimedes translations to gain a more precise idea of the linguistic complexity of the formulaicity of these texts.

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